

Multifunctional strong-bonded 3-layered polymer coating on WE43 for drug-eluting stent applications

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Drug-eluting stents (DESs) are coated with antiproliferative drugs (e.g., paclitaxel and sirolimus), which are released from polymer carrier (mostly biodegradable) coatings on a metal substrate. Here the major problem is hydrogen gas formation on the surface of Mg during its degradation in the body environment which causes the polymer coating to peel off [1,2].

In this study, an oxide layer is used to increase the bonding strength between a Multifunctional 3-layered polymer coating (PCL-PLLA-PLGA) and WE43 as well as protect the WE43 against degradation [3]. The hydrophobic nature of polycaprolactone (PCL) acts as an anti-corrosion barrier as it prevents water uptake. Poly-L-lactic acid (PLLA) [4] acts as a bridge between the inner and outer layer and finally, FDA-approved biocompatible Poly Lactic-co-Glycolic Acid (PLGA) is used as a drug carrier Fig (1-a) [5].

The oxide layer was formed on the surface using the anodizing method in a 1 mol/l NaOH bath Fig (1-b,1-c). Potentiodynamic polarization and Electrochemical Impedance Spectroscopy results show that the Oxide layer itself can increase the corrosion resistance a lot (1-d,1-e). In addition, the oxide layer increased the roughness causing stronger adhesion for polymer coating. This oxide layer has a drawback which is its hydrophilicity. This can be overcome by adding a thin Stearic Acid layer on the surface. The contact angle of the oxide layer increased from approximately 15° to above 100°.

In conclusion, this study is still in progress and in vitro analysis will be considered after finalizing each polymer coating on WE43 to achieve a good profile of properties based on coating thickness.

Figure 1: (a) Schematic of 3-layered polymer coating on WE43, (b) Cross-section image of oxide layer (c) Oxide layer microstructure (d) EIS and (e) PDP diagram.

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